

ENGLISH IN THE STATUS OF THE LANGUAGE OF WORLD COMMUNICATION IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article talks about the importance of learning English. In addition, the reasons for the formation of English as a foreign language throughout the world are indicated. The influence of the English language in the learning process is the focus of this work.

Key words: English, communication, communication goals, language education, globalization
An unprecedented phenomenon in the world language system, namely the transformation of English into a global language as a result of the information revolution and the globalization of all aspects of human activity, is changing the generally accepted ideas about foreign languages and the concept of literacy. One of the first to announce a change in the educational paradigm was the Brazilian webmaster R. Schutz, who developed the educational website "English Made in Brazil" and led a group of authors publishing language materials and research on this site. In the article "English is an international language", first posted on the site on December 20, 2002, Schutz drew the attention of site visitors to social changes in the course of history, which led to the fact that illiteracy, which was a common phenomenon in the Middle Ages, when there were even professional scribes for writing letters, was replaced within a few centuries by universal literacy of the population. Thus, the literacy rate in Europe in 1700 was from 30 to 40 percent. By the middle of the XIX century, literacy had reached 55 percent and was already considered as the main qualification in human society. Today, lack of education in developed countries has actually been eliminated. If traditional education includes the skills and abilities related to reading, writing and oral numeracy in the concept of literacy, then, according to Schutz, the ability to speak English as a second language of the speaker will soon need to be included in the concept of elementary literacy. Schutz believes that English can no longer be considered as a foreign language, since the possession of it as a means of universal communication is a mandatory part of education. "By choosing English as the world language," he declares Schutz, – history condemned monolingualism in the near future the future of illiteracy" [1].

The implicit recognition of the new educational paradigm, according to which English is no longer actually considered as a "foreign language", but as a prerequisite for "ensuring the participation of all Europeans in a new knowledge-based society", is also evidenced by the documents of the European Commission "Framework Strategy for Multilingualism to improve the effectiveness of mastering language skills" from 2000. and the "New Framework Strategy for Multilingualism" of 2005, which set the task for European educational systems to achieve the mastery of Europeans "practical skills and abilities in at least two languages other than their native" [2, 3]. The "New Framework Strategy" states that a multilingual society cannot be built if the trend persists in which learning a foreign language means only learning English [3].

Even more convincingly, the trend of changing the attitude of linguists and the political elite to the status of the English language and their recognition of the change in the educational paradigm is observed on the material of studies of the development of the English language, carried out by D. Graddol on behalf of the British Council and published in 1997 and 2006. In the first study, entitled "The Future of English" [4], Graddol, in his own words, "analyzes the complex combination of material and cultural trends that will shape the global fate of the English language," and concludes that "the future is more complex and less more predictable than expected" [4. p. 1]. The author of the study refers to the opinion of the scientific community about the advent of a new "world order" in the XXI century, in which the Internet and information technologies can lead to changes in traditional ways of communication. Graddol believes that in the new "world era that humanity has entered, language and communication will play a more central role than before in economic, political and cultural life "just at the historical moment when a global language emerged" [4. p. 3]. The study emphasizes the role of the English language as an important element of global scientific, technological, economic and cultural development, but gives a cautious assessment of the trend of linguistic dominance of the English language in the future: "We cannot just extrapolate on the basis of recent decades and assume that this trend will continue without change" [4. p. 4]. Over the next decade, the pace of globalization of the English language not only did not decrease, but even increased. The global status of the English language is evidenced by the data of its use in the tourism industry. In 2004, in 74 percent of cases, English was used in international tourism as a means of interlanguage communication among non-native speakers. Only 4 percent of the use of English was in contacts between people for whom English was their first language, and in 22 percent of cases English was used in contacts between native and non-native English speakers [5. p. 29].

The following study by D. Graddol, published by the British Council in 2006, presents the development of the English language for the next decade as a period of its unconditional triumph as a global language in virtually all spheres of human activity. According to the forecast of this study, by the end of this period, three billion people will speak English, which is almost five times the population of countries in which English is the official language [5]. The change in the attitude of the British Council to the development of the English language is evidenced by the very name of the study, which, in contrast to the uncertainty characteristic of the study published in 1997, directly indicates the new status of the language and the departure from the consideration of English as a foreign language: "Why global English may mean the end of English as a foreign language" [5].

Transformation of English into a global language the language of universal communication and the widespread transition to its study not as a foreign language (English as a foreign language, EFL), but as a second language (English as a second language, ESL), also require the rejection of the traditional model of the dissemination and use of English in the world in the form of three concentric circles, first proposed by an American linguist of Indian origin of Br. Kachru in the seminal article "Standards, Codification and Sociolinguistic Realism: English in the Outer Circle" (1985) [6]. According to the Kachru model, three concentric circles, internal, external and expanding, represent "types of dissemination, models of assimilation and functional domains in which English is used as a means of intercultural and interlanguage communication" [6. pp. 11-36]. In the inner circle, which includes the main English-speaking

countries (Great Britain, USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, etc.), English is the mother tongue for the majority of the population (L1). In the outer circle, which includes countries in which English is not the native language for the majority of the population, but, due to its special importance. In public administration, education and economics, it has the status of a second language (L2) and is studied as ESL (English as a second language). The outer circle includes India, Pakistan, Philippines, Nigeria and other countries where English is the official language. The expanding circle includes all countries in which English is not the mother tongue or the second language for the majority of the population, is not used in management and education and is studied in the school system as a foreign language (EFL).

The changes that took place in the world by the end of the XX century led D. Graddol to the conclusion, expressed by him in the study of the development of the English language (1997), that the model of concentric circles of Kachru "will not be the most useful model for describing the use of the English language in the XXI century" [4. p. 10]. Graddol's criticism of the Kachru model was based on a "shift in the center of gravity" from speakers of English as a native language to speakers of English as a second language. According to Graddall, with the growing number of speakers of English as a second language, the future of the English language will be determined to a large extent by them, and not by "native speakers". Accordingly, instead of concentric circles, Graddol proposed three partially overlapping circles.

In this study, Graddol still considers it acceptable in relation to the English language to use terminology according to which all English speakers are divided into three groups: speakers of the language as the first (L1), speakers of the language as the second (L2), and speakers of the language as a foreign language (EFL). Explaining the difference between the categories of speakers of English as a second and a foreign language, he writes: "The main difference between speaking fluent English as a foreign language and speaking English as a second language depends on whether English is used in the country and in the family of speakers and, thus, whether it determines the language the repertoire of his personality" [4. p. 11].

References:

1. Schütz R. English – The International Language // English Made in Brazil. URL: <http://www.sk.com.br/sk.ingl.htm/>. Retrieved: 08.10.2023.
2. Education & Training 2010: Work program adopted by the European Commission in 2001 // ETUCE Circular 2/2005.
3. A New Framework Strategy for Multilingualism // COM (2005) 596 final. Brussels, 2005.
4. Graddol D. The Future of English? A guide to forecasting the popularity of the English language in the 21st century. London : The British Council, 2000.
5. Graddol D. English Next: Why Global English May Mean the End of English as a Foreign Language. London : The British Council, 2006.
6. Kachru B. Standards codification and sociolinguistic realism: The English language in the outer circle // English in the world: Teaching and learning the
7. language and literatures / eds. by R. Quirk and H. Widdowson. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 1985.